

THE IMPORTANCE AND PRINCIPLES OF MANAGEMENT IN AGRICULTURE

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Introduction: In independent Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to reforming the system of conditions for sustainable economic development. management plays a key role in the economy of the republic, and its development is to some extent connected with the social and cultural life of the majority of the population living in rural areas . In order to do fulfil the tasks necessary for the life of society, the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan must be able to meet the requirements of modern scientific and technological development, to rely on new achievements of scientific and technological development. The achievements of modern scientific and technological development are used not only in the creation of modern production technologies, but also in the scientific organization of labor, the development of effective methods of management. The experience of modern business leaders shows that the factors of management and its organization play a decisive role in the achieved success. Reform of the management system in agriculture, which is an important method of management in agriculture and includes a set of tools to influence economic interests, is a great importance in the proper solution of issues of interest. the relevance of the study of management issues in agriculture is enhanced by the introduction of qualitatively new property relations in the economy and the expansion of economic

independence of business entities. It is also due to the need to create a broad economic framework, as noted by President I.A.Karimov: "An economic environment that encourages active labor, allows everyone to realize their potential and earn a living through their participation in labor ..."

Analysis and results: Factors such as the laws governing the formation of management systems also have a significant impact on the system . They can be called principles. The principle of purpose requires that in the formation of the system is connected with its goals. Each goal must be "owned" within the system. But from an organizational point of view, the existence of systemic bugs of ammunition that are not responsible for the specific goals of management is also unacceptable. Another principle of the formation of management systems is the unity of management. Each agency should have one leader or one head for each example. Another principle is the scope of management. It is determined by the maximum number of p offices in each level that a single higher-level office can effectively manage . In the current era of market reforms and in the context of complex systems, a single office can manage no less than a dozen bugs. Also, the current stage of development requires the emergence of the principle of trust in authority. The more fully entrusted the authority is, the more opportunities there will be for it to focus on the coordination and control of the overall leadership, that is, on the performance of tasks that no subordinate can replace today. Depending on the type of relationship between the management of agricultural production, systems can be divided into three main types - regular, is 22 official, functional and mixed, i.e. combined. The simplest systems are regular systems. In them, each group of agencies at a single level will have its own governing body at the highest level, based on the levels of management. A group of second-tier offices has a third-tier leadership boogie, and so on.

In a regular system, all management issues are addressed through a single channel. This creates a lot of precision and accuracy. In regular systems, the higher authority must be omnipresent in all matters, as subordinate bodies have the sole right to refer to it. The limited scope of management leads to an increase in the number of offices at the same level. As a result, the flexibility of regular systems is lost. The basis

of functional systems is based on the idea of specialization . At the same time, certain issues are attached to each department. For example, one office deals with accounting, another with technology, and a third with marketing. Due to the limited scope of jurisdiction, a specialized agency has the potential to improve the quality of decisions made in principle. But the presence of multiple functional heads in a single subordinate office brings with it a unique complexity. Mixed systems - regular and limited functional mixed systems - play an important role in overcoming the difficulties inherent in regular and functional systems. - target system is a separate type of mixed systems . Forming a clear system of governance is a creative process. However, if scientifically developed model forms of the system are used, this will make the work even easier. In this context , all the structural divisions of the management office unite the five main groups.

The first is the structural units that manage the management facilities. The main issue is not to overestimate the scope of management , but on the other hand, the inability to create very small divisions to manage small facilities.

The second is the main functional system, ie planning, accounting and control units.

The third is the functions of marketing, ie supply, sales, science and technology.

The fourth is the auxiliary and service units, i.e. the office, the archive, and so on.

The fifth is the head of the department, his deputies, the association, the council, and so on.

Systemic improvement is an important opportunity to raise the spirit to a higher level. However, it should be applied only if there is a need for reorganization. Informal relationships in the existing system should be taken into account when reorganizing the serious costs associated with changing traditions. At present, the management pays a lot of attention to working with staff, the use of technical means, the introduction of new methods. The most important task of personnel policy is to develop the requirements for management. The management system employee must have the necessary business qualities as well as be knowledgeable. Organizational skills, a sense of innovation, the ability to appreciate new technical and organizational ideas, skill in

their application, as well as one of the most important business qualities - efficiency are the main requirements for the employee. In the system of working with management staff, the object and the subject are divided as follows. The object is the main elements of the system of work with employees, which are the selection, evaluation and so on . An entity is a collection of agencies and employees that perform the function of working with employees. One of the main points of the system of working with farm workers is the choice: its principles, order, methods. This structure of work with employees includes: hiring, reserve, bottom-up, rotation, replacement, resignation.

The role of the leader in the production process is well known. The manager, no matter what position he holds, cannot change these roles, but performs them in a way that is unique to him. The roles of a leader are: interpersonal, informational, and decision-making. The interpersonal role of the leader is defined by the role and function of the leader. To fulfil the information role, the manager takes information from the production and external environments and plays the role of decision-making based on its analysis and puts it into practice. For example, it rationally allocates resources in agricultural production and has its own solution to situations that occur. In management activities, management functions are performed by senior managers. Management of agricultural production is the process of achieving the main goal of the organization, which consists of planning, analysis, propensity and control functions. Land reclamation, mechanization of agriculture, electrification, chemical engineering, increasing crop yields, expecting labor productivity are crucial . The development of industries that provide the means of agricultural production in the country will strengthen its material and technical base. The main processes in the cultivation of agricultural products have been mechanized and the use of manual labor has been considerably reduced. In agriculture, the main field work, plowing, sowing, simultaneous fertilization, harvesting of cereals, etc., is fully mechanized, 78% of which is mechanized, especially in cotton growing. More than 30% of cotton produced in the country is harvested by machines. Agricultural cooperatives - lifelong inheritance of members of companies, employees of other agricultural and forestry

enterprises, institutions and organizations to their families, as well as families of teachers, doctors and other specialists living in rural areas, inherited in the manner prescribed by law .

The plot of land is given up to 0.35 hectares on irrigated lands and up to 0.5 hectares on non-irrigated arable lands, and up to 1 hectare on non-irrigated arable lands in deserts and deserts, including the area occupied by buildings and courtyards. citizens ,to inherit lifelong plots of land within the framework of farming 0,06 hectares can be realized on the basis of an auction. The decision to allocate a plot of land to a farm is made by the district governor on the basis of the decision of the general meeting of the company, the supreme and governing body of the agricultural enterprise, institution and organization, the employer, at the same time as the decision to establish a farm. newly established farm is exercised by persons who have lived in the area permanently for at least three years, except for newly developed land plots. The decision of the management of the company's farm, the governing body of another agricultural enterprise, institution and organization, the employer and the district governor to refuse to allocate a plot of land for the establishment of a farm may be appealed in court.

The following scientific conclusions were made during the research: The political , economical and spiritual changes that have taken place in our country have increased the importance and weight of the science of management in agriculture. In order to fulfil the tasks necessary for the life of society, the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan must be able to meet the requirements of modern scientific and technological development, to rely on new achievements in the development of science and technology. It is well known that the practice of management in agriculture has undergone a long and profound historical development. In the early days of human development, the entrepreneur, the property owner, managed the production based on his own experience. In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to reforming the system of conditions for sustainable economic development. Agriculture plays a key role in the economy of the Republic, and its development plays an important role in ensuring the well-being of the population of the Republic . The achievements of modern scientific and technical development are used not only in the creation of modern production

technologies, but also in the scientific organization of labor, the development of effective methods of management. The experience of modern business leaders shows that management and organizational factors play a crucial role in the success achieved. At present, the theory and technology of management in agriculture is an integral part of modern production technology of management.

Conclusions and suggestions

The achievements of modern scientific and technical development are used not only in the creation of modern production technologies, but also in the scientific organization of labor, the development of effective methods of management. The experience of modern business leaders shows that management and organizational factors play a crucial role in the success achieved. At present, the theory and technology of management in agriculture is an integral part of modern production technology of management.

Based on the above, the following scientific proposals and practical recommendations have been developed for the prospects of increasing and developing the effectiveness of management in agriculture in the context of economic liberalization :

1. Management in agriculture always requires the search for ways to activate the innovative activities of employees and ways to encourage them ;
2. Management in agriculture is a system of current and long-term planning, forecasting, organization, sale of services and products of agricultural development for profit;
3. In agriculture, a manager is a specialist in the field of organization, management, sales and services, with a certain degree of administrative and economic independence . All over the world, a manager is required to know how to work effectively, that is, profitably. technical, technological and other decisions made by the manager in agriculture should be based on clear economic calculations. The quality of the product should also be high, and the cost of its production should not be too high .

4. Today, farm managers in Uzbekistan must be aware of the science of agricultural management.

If the leader has a thorough knowledge, he will be able to run the business well. Managers must always look for the right and efficient way out of resources and costs.

5. through the development of market mechanisms in agriculture, the improvement of property relations, as well as on the basis of the broad development of companies, farmers, dehkans and private subsidiary farms . it is necessary to adequately organize the service sector in agriculture

6. One of the key components of entrepreneurship in agricultural management is the business plan. Any business will succeed if it is based on a plan. When the necessary calculations are made in advance, the possibilities are fully taken into account, the work is fully imagined, it is sure that it will be realized, and it is possible to start it boldly. These lines should be reflected in the business plan based on agricultural management.

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